
Analysis of the Effect of Knowledge on the Implementation of Management Functions of Public Health Centers in Bengkulu Province

Yandrizarl¹, Titin Sumarni²

^{1,2}Widyaiswara Ahli Madya UPTD Pelatihan Kesehatan Bengkulu.

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Community Health Center carrying out the authority task to implement the stages of management functions. The application of management requires good knowledge to be able to implement planning, mobilizing implementation, monitoring, and controlling assessments optimally.

MATERIALS/METHODS: The research was conducted using a quantitative method with a cross-sectional approach. The research population is the Head in charge of health efforts at Public Health Center throughout Bengkulu Province. The data was collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using the Chi-Square Test with the help of the SPSS 22 application.

RESULT: The research affects planning knowledge, Organizing Actuating, monitoring, and linearly controlling the assessment. Knowledge of supervision control appraisal has less effect on the implementation of management functions simultaneously.

Conclusion: Applying knowledge management in health services will improve service quality for targeted and sustainable services. Knowledge management in health services can be improved to help improve the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of services. Mobilizing the implementation of health programs must pay attention to available resources to optimize their respective roles and functions. Resource based mobilization is useful in adding perspective to knowledge mobilization in healthcare organizations.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Implementation of management functions

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INTRODUCTION

The organizers of the Public health center function apply the management stages as stated in the Minister of Health Regulation number 44 of 2016 concerning Public Health Center management. Management consists of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling to achieve goals/objectives effectively and efficiently. Effective means that the expected goals can be achieved through a good, correct, and quality implementation process based on situational analysis results supported by accurate data and information. While efficient means how Public Health Center utilize available resources to carry out health efforts according to standards properly and correctly, they can realize the performance targets that have been set (1).

The healthcare environment is dynamic, complex, complicated, and challenging. Healthcare organizations face serious challenges today, especially regarding quality,

effectiveness, and efficiency. Healthcare managers and leaders must adopt a new approach to adapt their

Organizations to the changing internal and external environment and the healthcare unit. Strategic management is not about predicting the future but about preparing for it and knowing what steps the company will take to implement its strategic plans and achieve competitive advantage (2).

Intangible assets, mainly intellectual capital, play a crucial role in helping organizations achieve higher levels of organizational performance (3). Knowledge has taken over other forms of resources, including capital (4). The implementation of management functions requires knowledge and skills for Public Health Center managers to be able to implement them optimally. In achieving performance, each Public Health Center must optimize the management functions of each program/activity. The problem is that applying management functions is not optimal for achieving

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performance. It is necessary to analyze the influence of knowledge on implementing management functions.

METHODS

The quantitative research method with a cross-sectional approach is to determine the effect of knowledge on the implementation of the management functions of the Public Health Center. Knowledge is an independent variable, and the management function is the dependent variable. Data collection uses an instrument that contains a list of knowledge questions about planning (P1), Organizing actuating (P2), Supervision Control Assessment (P3), and Implementation of

management functions. The population of this research is the manager of Public Health Center in Bengkulu Province, with a total of 166 samples. Linear and multiple regression analysis using SPSS 22 to analyze the knowledge that affects the function's implementation.

RESULTS

The results of the Chi-square test analysis aim to determine the independent variables of the influence between knowledge on planning implementation (P1), Organizing actuating (P2), Supervision control, assessment can be seen in table 1 and table 2.

Table 1. Chi-Square Test

		Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Planning	Pearson Chi-Square	48.676 ^a	1	.000
Driving Imprementation	Pearson Chi-Square	45.330 ^a	1	.000
Supervision Control Appraisal	Pearson Chi-Square	27.069 ^a	1	.000

The results of table 1 obtained a p-value <0.05, it can be concluded that there is an influence of knowledge on the implementation of planning, Organizing Actuating, Supervision Control, Assessment.

The binomial test is used to determine whether there is a joint influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable

Table 2. Variables in the Equation

		B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95,0% C.I.for EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Step 1 ^a	Implem_ planning (P1)	-1.516	.498	9.276	1	.002	.220	.083	.582
	Implem_ Organizing Actuating (P2)	-1.149	.552	4.340	1	.037	.317	.108	.934
	Implem_ Supervision Control, Assessment (P3)	-.415	.472	.772	1	.380	.660	.262	1.667
	Constant	1.627	.269	36.533	1	.000	5.089		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Implem_P1, Implem_P2, Implem_P3.

Based on Table 2 Variables in the equation above: the independent variable P1 P value 0.002 <0.05, and P2 P value 0.037 <0.05, meaning that knowledge has an influence on planning implementation (P1) and Organizing actuating (P2). While the independent variable P3 value P value 0.380 > 0.05, meaning that knowledge does not affect the implementation of Supervision Control, Assessment (P3).

DISCUSSION

Planning Implementation

Knowledge of Public Health Center managers influences planning implementation in managing health programs at Public Health Center. Planning application requires knowledge of analyzing and collecting data to produce information as the primary material for preparation. Donate (2015) emphasizes the importance of knowledge

management and competitive intelligence, which influences the strategic management process. Knowledge management positively and significantly impacts the strategic management process (5). Studies showing knowledge management's important role in determining organizational strategic policies show significant positive results.

Better knowledge management in the organization will support the process of making policies and implementing organizational strategies that help performance improvement. The study shows the vital role of knowledge management in developing and increasing the reliability of organizational strategies in facing the market demands of a dynamic society. The strategic policy will determine whether the organization is on the right track to face competition (6). Knowledge management in healthcare is progressing, and the complexities and challenges facing the

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health care sector can be overcome by adopting a knowledge management strategy. The use of knowledge management in health services promises to improve the quality of service for patients and the community by providing sustainable services. The current state of knowledge management in health services can be improved to help improve the quality of patient care globally and efficiency in health services (7).

Competitive intelligence has a significant positive effect on the strategic management process in organizations because many studies have shown similar results (8). How organizations use market related data and information for decision making significantly influences how organizations plan strategies systematically, execute strategies with commitment and consistency and evaluate continuous improvement. When the organization is able to properly take into account various market possibilities, the organization can anticipate various steps to deal with the dynamics of change will be better in strategic planning (6). The planning of the Public Health Center is prepared based on the results of the situational analysis in the form of program/activity achievements, introspection surveys and village community consultations on health issues, national, provincial, and district program policies, achievements of the healthy Indonesia program with a family approach (PIS-PK). Preparing the results of the analysis into a practical and targeted plan requires sufficient planning knowledge.

Organizing Actuating Implementation

The results showed a significant effect of knowledge and driving the implementation of health programs at the Public Health Center. The application of driving implementation requires knowledge to optimize the available resources to be efficient and effective in achieving goals. Mobilizing human resources requires the ability to motivate and guide so that implementers can work optimally. According to Bosua (2014), leaders need to be aware of their roles as mentors, organizers, and content editors and their responsibilities to contribute to the mobilization of knowledge within the organization (9). There must be an appreciation of the role and commitment of managers to facilitate and support activities related to the transfer of knowledge to implementers. Knowledge transfer is essential in most cases where employees take on some of the roles and responsibilities assigned to them. Create a formal portfolio or job description for one or more of these roles in the organization. Relationships with cross-programs and cross-sectors related to empowering available resources for implementing health programs require the transfer of knowledge from the leadership to other managers to optimize the human resources available from outside the organization.

Knowledge-based work contexts and roles such as knowledge mentors have proven useful by providing timely

guidance to project implementers and creating an open environment to mobilize expertise and make knowledge accessible to required implementers. Continuous efforts to improve knowledge mobilization in an organizational context can encourage the creation and formalization of new knowledge mobilization roles and responsibilities within an organization. (9). The integrative model that explains the relationship between organizational factors, knowledge transfer, and innovative ability shows organizational factors' direct and indirect effects on knowledge transfer and innovation. (10). Mobilizing the implementation of available resources requires knowledge of organizing, empowering communities, and negotiating across sectors. Organizers need knowledge of identifying organizational resources and the elements' roles and functions. The routine mobilization is carried out by the Public health center monthly in mini-workshops. Mini workshops carried out effectively will be able to mobilize all available resources such as health personnel, funds, methods, regulations, equipment, community resources, cadres, and community leaders, as well as cross sectoral resources. Multiple models are needed to adapt to different environments. Improve the performance of health service organizations and interdependence of existing health service organizations in certain areas. Health system reform tries to improve the internal ability of the organization and the environment to produce the desired results (11).

Mobilizing the implementation of health programs must pay attention to available resources to optimize their respective roles and functions. Resource based mobilization helps add perspective to knowledge mobilization in healthcare organizations. Organization level competencies and a more micro level focus are particularly suited to the public organization arena. Invest in building underlying core competencies over the long term, particularly high capacity. In conditions of a limited budget, the service system needs to learn knowledge management in the management of health services. Community empowerment must be optimized to be involved from planning, and implementation to evaluation, so that the planned activities receive support. The limited sources of funds at the Public Health Center require the leaders and persons in charge of health efforts to increase their knowledge of mobilizing the available resources. The Head of the Public Health Center and the person in charge of health efforts are leaders who must be able to mobilize human resources. Leaders must develop leadership qualities and strategies based on a theory with empirical support and evidence about health care success.

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Implementation of Supervision Control Assessment

Knowledge affects the implementation supervision control Assessment (P3) health programs at the Public Health Center. Supervision is a process to improve the performance of public health workers in providing quality health services. Effective and sustainable monitoring strategies help address the challenges faced by officers. The implementation of supervision by the leaders and managers of Public health center requires knowledge of supervisory management to effectively supervise the implementation of activities. Oversight by providing a detailed quality improvement plan paired with ongoing monitoring and feedback improves the performance of multiple standards and processes. (12). Supervision carried out using predetermined criteria will be more effective in carrying out supervision of activity implementers and can evaluate activities effectively and find solutions for improvement. Inadequate infrastructure contributes to poor health quality in service delivery, and Public Health Center staff lack incentives to implement process improvements that require extra improvement efforts.(12). The implementation of supervision must be accompanied by incentives following the provisions so that officers in carrying out activities work as well as possible.

Based on the test results of the effect of knowledge on planning, driving implementation, and monitoring the control of the assessment simultaneously, the supervision of the control of the assessment has less impact on the implementation of the management function of the Public Health Center. Supportive supervision has the potential to improve service quality, improve the skills of health workers and improve performance. Effective supportive supervision and how different supervisory approaches affect performance in social and cultural contexts needs to be improved. A methodological shift that builds capacity at lower levels of service delivery to internal support oversight, especially in health facilities, will reduce systemic and logistical implementation challenges. (13). The paradigm of regular external management and the funding and logistical requirements accompany follow-up in many low-income countries. The quality of supportive supervision compared to frequency, human interactions built on trust, confidentiality, empathy, and an emphasis on task assistance are essential (13). The leadership of the Puskesmas, in carrying out supervision, must pay attention to the readiness of the standards to be applied, the knowledge and skills of officers, efforts to solve problems, and incentives for officers who work well.

The effect of supportive supervision: Several studies have linked supportive supervision to positive outcomes such as job motivation, retention, satisfaction, and better performance (14). The supervisory dimensions of task assistance, emotional support, and interpersonal interaction benefit health workers. Improving the quality of supervision

has a greater impact than increasing the frequency of supervision(15). The combined approach has shown some positive results. (George et al) documented an initiative in Uganda that utilized mentoring with a combination of external specialist teams and local mentors, resulting in more productivity, improved problem identification and solving, and improved patient management and healthcare worker skills (16). The person in charge of the health effort and program coordinator at the Public Health Center must be able to carry out the function of a supervisor to oversee the implementation of the program or activity that is the responsibility. The implementation of effective and continuous supervision consistently by the coordinator or person in charge of health efforts towards the implementing activities will be able to monitor the achievement of performance.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge affects planning, Organizing Actuating, Supervision Control, and Assessment. Simultaneous testing of knowledge has less effect on implementing assessment control supervision. Applying knowledge management in health services will improve the quality of services for sustainable targets and services. Knowledge management in health services can be improved to help improve the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of services. Mobilizing the implementation of health programs must pay attention to available resources to optimize their respective roles and functions. Resource based mobilization helps add perspective to knowledge mobilization in healthcare organizations. In conditions of a limited budget, the service system needs to learn knowledge management in the management of health services. Supportive supervision has the potential to improve service quality, improve the skills of health workers and improve performance. Effective supportive supervision with different supervisory approaches affecting performance in social and cultural contexts needs to be improved.

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